

limiting molar conductance (μ_0) cannot be obtained by the usual extrapolation method, and Debye-Hückel-Onsager equation is not applicable to these soap solutions.

Since these soaps in dilute solutions behave as weak electrolytes, an expression for the dissociation of calcium soaps can be developed in Ostwald's manner³. The dissociation constant, K can be expressed as

$$K = \frac{4C^2\alpha^3}{(1-\alpha)} \quad (1)$$

Replacing the degree of dissociation, α , by the conductance ratio, μ/μ_0 and rearranging, one obtains,

$$\mu^2 C^2 = \frac{K\mu_0^3}{4\mu} - \frac{K\mu_0^2}{4} \quad (2)$$

The values of μ_0 and K have been obtained from the slope [$K\mu_0^3/4$] and intercept [$-K\mu_0^2/4$] of the plots of $\mu^2 C^2$ vs $1/\mu$ below the CMC. The values of μ_0 are 7.1 and 5.8 for a solvent mixture containing 50% chloroform and are 1.1 and 1.2 for a mixture of 70% chloroform while the values of K are 2.6×10^{-5} and 2.3×10^{-5} for 50% chloroform and 3.7×10^{-5} and 4.1×10^{-5} for 70% chloroform for calcium caproate and valerate, respectively.

The values of α , calculated by assuming it as equal to the conductance ratio μ/μ_0 and using the value of μ_0 obtained from the plots of $\mu^2 C^2$ vs $1/\mu$ lie between 0.70 and 0.32, which shows that these soaps behave as weak electrolytes in solutions.

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Thermal Diffusion of Aqueous Magnesium Chloride in an Acid Soil

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THERE have been reports on studies of thermal diffusion of water in soil¹⁻⁴. However, such investigations with aqueous solutions of electro-

lytes have been rather rare. More recently, Sanyal *et al.*⁵⁻⁹ have re-examined the thermodynamic theories of thermal diffusion and pointed out the significance of heat and entropy of transport in characterising the soil-moisture interactions. The present paper gives the results of a study on thermal diffusion of aqueous $MgCl_2$ solution in an acid soil from the district of Jalpaiguri, West Bengal.

The theoretical treatment used is an adaptation of the one based on non-equilibrium thermodynamics and developed by Mukherjee and Sanyal¹⁰ for dealing with diffusion of a solution through an 'open' membrane subjected to a temperature gradient. The expression, giving the heat of transport ($\hat{Q}$) of a dilute solution across the soil chamber, reads^{9,10}

$$\hat{Q} = RT^2\sigma_1 B_1 - T(\bar{V}_1 + \bar{V}_0) \left(\frac{\Delta P - \Delta\pi}{\Delta T} \right)_{st} \quad (1)$$

where, $\bar{V}_1$ and $\bar{V}_0$ are the partial molal volume of the solute and solvent respectively, ΔP and $\Delta\pi$ are the hydrostatic and osmotic pressure differences between the two terminal solution chambers. σ_1 , the 'Soret coefficient' of the solute, is given by the relation,

$$\sigma_1 = -\frac{1}{\bar{m}_1} \left(\frac{\Delta m}{\Delta T} \right)_{st}$$

where, $\bar{m}_1$ is the mean molal concentration; the thermodynamic factor B_1 is given by

$$B_1 = \left(1 + \frac{\Delta \ln \gamma_1}{\Delta \ln m_1} \right)_{\tau}$$

where, γ_1 is the mean ionic activity coefficient of the solute. Experimentally the term in $\left(\frac{\Delta P - \Delta\pi}{\Delta T} \right)_{st}$

turns out to be negligible for dilute solutions, being at least two orders of magnitude lower than the term in σ_1 , and hence equation (1) approximates to

$$\hat{Q} = RT^2\sigma_1 B_1 \quad (2)$$

$\hat{Q}$ is known to be sensitive to the nature of interactions in the system^{5,10}, and is defined to be the amount of heat absorbed per mole of a diffusing substance from the region it leaves, and released in the region it moves into under isothermal conditions¹¹.

Experimental

The non-isothermal diffusion cell used was similar to the one used by Cary and Taylor^{8,9} and Sanyal *et al.*⁶, and consisted of a three-chamber perspex box in which the soil compartment was sandwiched between, and separated from the two terminal solution chambers (of volume 245.0 cm³ each) by means of two porous ceramic plates. The solution in one compartment was heated by means of a coiled heater connected to a variable voltage supply, while the temperature of the solution in the other terminal chamber was kept lower (which was higher than the ambient temperature) by virtue

TABLE 1—HEAT OF TRANSPORT OF AQUEOUS MAGNESIUM CHLORIDE IN AN ACID SOIL AT THREE-FOURTH OF THE CORRESPONDING FULL (SOIL) WATER HOLDING CAPACITY

Mean concn. M	T K	ΔT deg.	$(\Delta_m)_{st} \times 10^3 M$	$\sigma_1 \times 10^3 K^{-1}$	B_1	$\hat{Q} = RT^2 \sigma_1 B_1$ kJ mol $^{-1}$
0.0125	321.0	22.3	0.470	-1.64	0.8784	-1.24 (± 0.03)
0.0250	319.0	23.4	0.600	-1.03	0.8556	-0.717 (± 0.008)
0.0500	320.1	17.3	0.325	-0.379	0.8556	-0.276 (± 0.006)
0.1000	318.7	16.9	0.300	-0.179	0.8556	-0.129 (± 0.006)
0.1500	318.5	14.9	1.300	-0.590	0.8556	-0.426 (± 0.003)
0.2000	322.5	20.2	2.300	-0.583	0.8556	-0.431 (± 0.006)

of circulating water from a thermostat through a glass coil located inside. Both the heater and the glass coil were placed towards the bottom of the appropriate terminal chambers, thereby allowing natural convection to set in, and keep the concentration in each such solution compartment uniform throughout the diffusion experiment.

The temperature in course of the experiment across each ceramic plate was monitored using copper-constantan thermocouple. The soil (an acid soil from West Bengal, having pH, 5.02; C.E.C., 8.7 meq/100 g; organic carbon, 1.6%; clay 12.4%; water holding capacity (whc), 58% moisture) was moistened to the desired degree (43.5% moisture by weight), and placed in the central compartment of the diffusion cell by maintaining a bulk density of 1.30 g cm $^{-3}$. The terminal chambers were filled with the same aqueous MgCl $_2$ solution (0.0125–0.2 M solution, prepared by dissolving the AnalaR salt in double-distilled and deaerated water of conductivity $< 3 \mu\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and placed in the terminal chambers one after another) by taking due care to eliminate any entrapped air from the whole system.

The entire set-up was placed inside an air thermostat, maintained at the mean temperature of the experiment. The exposed portions of the glass U-tubes as well as the separating funnels were kept covered with glass-wool to ensure thermal insulation. Once the steady state was attained (as indicated by the solution levels in the two short U-tubes becoming stationary), suitable aliquots were withdrawn from both the solution chambers and the concentration differences of MgCl $_2$ were measured by titrations against a standard EDTA solution using erichrome black T as an indicator.

The thermodynamic factor (B_1) was computed from the corresponding activity coefficient data for aqueous MgCl $_2$ solution at various concentrations; the latter were calculated by using the relation 12 ,

$$\log \gamma_{\pm} = \log \gamma_{\text{CaCl}_2} + m \times \frac{4}{5} \Delta B'$$

where, B' is the deviation function introduced by Scatchard 11 . The necessary activity coefficient

data for aqueous CaCl $_2$ solutions were also noted from Lewis and Randall 13 .

A side experiment was conducted to measure the changes in the initial pH of the MgCl $_2$ solutions used after placing them in the terminal chambers (one after another) with the given acid soil kept in the central chamber of the diffusion cell, and allowing 6 h to lapse (which is the longest period of time required for the attainment of the steady state in the given studies). The pH changes turned out to be negligibly small, and appropriate calculations, utilising such pH change values, illustrated that the extent of exchange between Mg $^{2+}$ ion and the dominant cation (H $^+$) of the given acid soil was negligible, especially so in comparison with the Δm values recorded for MgCl $_2$ solutions at the steady state.

Results and Discussion

The results are incorporated in Table 1. The heat of transport ($\hat{Q}$), which is a mean of at least three determinations conducted under a given set of experimental condition, is seen to be negative for the chloride solution. These negative $\hat{Q}$ values correspond to an absorption of heat ahead of the diffusing entity and a liberation behind in course of diffusional transport through the soil. A plausible explanation may be sought in the light of local degree of ordering of water, i.e., 'electrostricted' water present in the ionic hydration hulls in the bulk solution, i.e., before the solution enters the soil chamber, and that in contact with the soil particles. Inasmuch as the influence of ion-dipole interactions in bringing down the 'local' entropy of water is expected to be weaker (especially so for a chloride) than that of the strong soil moisture retention phenomenon, particularly so for the given acid soil with a high organic matter content, the passage of the aqueous solutions through the soil chamber would indeed be accompanied by a liberation of heat behind and an absorption ahead, i.e. a negative $\hat{Q}$.

On closer examination, $\hat{Q}$ is seen to register a rise with increase in initial concentration of the chloride solutions, followed by a fall at still higher contributions (Table 1). The long-range ion-solvent interactions in the bulk solution are expected to make positive contributions to $\hat{Q}$ in dilute solutions. These contributions decrease at higher concentrations owing to a partial overlapping of the hydration zones (i.e., mutual screening effect of ions⁹). The latter causes a narrowing down of the aforesaid difference of ordering in water structure between the bulk and the given soil, leading to a less negative $\hat{Q}$ at higher concentrations.

However, at still higher concentrations (e.g., above 0.10–0.15 M; Table 1), ion-pairing may become important; the latter may lead to an enhancement of $\hat{Q}$ due to a net fall in the extent of long-range ordering in water. It is indeed interesting to note in this connection that a minimum in the activity coefficient of aqueous MgCl₂ solutions occurs within the concentration range 0.4–0.5 M as well.

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Apparent Molar Volumes of L-Proline and L-Hydroxyproline in Methanol-Water Mixtures

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AMINO acids have been quite useful as models¹ for understanding the thermodynamic behaviour of peptides and proteins in solution. Volumetric properties and heat capacities of amino acids in

different aquo-organic media have been investigated¹⁻⁴. But similar investigations at different temperatures are rather scarce although such a study is likely to give an insight into the mode of solute-solvent interactions. As an extension of our studies^{5,6} of apparent molar volumes of amino acids in water and methanol-water mixtures, we report herein the apparent molar volumes of L-proline and L-hydroxyproline in methanol-water mixtures.

Experimental

L-Proline and L-hydroxyproline were (LOBA and E. Merck, G. R.) were used as such and dried before use under reduced pressure for 40 h and stored over anhydrous calcium chloride in vacuum desiccator. Methanol (AnalaR) was purified by the recommended method⁷. All the solutions were prepared by weight on molar basis in double-distilled degassed water and vacuum corrected. The procedure for density measurements have been described previously⁸. The density data were accurate within $\pm 3 \times 10^{-5}$ g cm⁻³.

Results and Discussion

The densities measured at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K have been used to calculate the apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) of the solute using equation (1),

$$\phi_v = \frac{1000(d_o - d)}{c d_o} + \frac{M}{d_o} \quad (1)$$

in which the terms have their usual significance. The plots of ϕ_v against concentration are linear and have positive slopes in case of both the amino acids in the temperature range studied. Limiting apparent molar volumes, ϕ_v^0 are obtained using least-square fit to the plot of the experimental values of ϕ_v against molar concentration, c , using equation (2),

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S_v c \quad (2)$$

where, $\phi_v^0 = \bar{V}^0$, is the infinite dilution partial molar volume and S_v the experimental slope. The values of ϕ_v^0 , S_v and standard errors, σ_v , obtained in 10, 20 and 30% (w/w) of methanol-water mixtures are listed in Table 1. The values of ϕ_v^0 in aqueous medium are also included in Table 1 along with the literature values. As seen from Table 1, the present ϕ_v^0 value of L-proline at 298.15 K agrees very well with the literature value⁹, but is slightly lower than the reported values⁹⁻¹¹. For L-hydroxyproline, there exists only one value for ϕ_v^0 at 298.15 K as reported by Ogawa *et al.*¹⁰ which is larger than the present value. The values of ϕ_v^0 at temperatures other than 298.15 K could not be compared due to lack of literature data. It is apparent from Table 1 that ϕ_v^0 increases with temperature in aqueous and methanol-water mixtures in the temperature range 298.15–318.15 K. It appears that primary and secondary solvation layers are formed around the zwitter ions. Since the solvent molecules from the